

Solid phase extraction, preconcentration of Cu^{II} and its separation from environmentally toxic metal ions with high molecular mass liquid cation exchanger, Versatic 9

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Abstract : A selective method has been developed for the extraction chromatographic trace level separation of Cu^{II} with Versatic 9 (liquid cation exchanger) coated on silanised silica gel. Cu^{II} has been extracted from 0.1 M acetate buffer at the range of pH 4.0–5.5. The effects of foreign ions, pH, flow-rate, stripping agents on extraction and elution have been investigated. Exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger at different temperatures with respect to Cu^{II} has been determined. The extraction equilibrium constant (K_{ex}) and different standard thermodynamic parameters have also been calculated by temperature variation method. The effect of pH on R_f values in ion exchange paper chromatography has been investigated. In order to investigate the sorption isotherm, two equilibrium models, the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms, were analyzed. Cu^{II} has been separated from synthetic binary and multi-component mixtures containing various metal ions associated with it in ores and alloy samples. The method effectively permits sequential separation of Cu^{II} from synthetic quaternary mixture containing its congeners Bi^{III}, Sn^{II}, Pb^{II} and Hg^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II} of same analytical group. The method was found effective for removal and recovery of Cu^{II} from industrial waste and standard alloy samples following its preconcentration on the column. A plausible mechanism for the extraction of Cu^{II} has been suggested.

Keywords : Versatic 9, Cu^{II}, separation, preconcentration, sorption isotherm.

Introduction

Copper is a harmful toxic element and has got a technical importance because of its high thermal and electrical conductance. In trace level heavy metals like Cr^{III}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} and Cu^{II} etc., are hazardous in waste samples to the environment¹. The removal of heavy metal ions from industrial waste waters is becoming more important with the increasing of industrial activities². Obviously trace level monitoring and removal of metallic toxicant poses a challenging problem to the analytical chemists. However, the preconcentration and separation of an analyte are usually necessary before its monitoring. During enrichment ultimately the target species is selectively gathered in a small volume from a large volume of sample of complex nature. Small amounts of metal pollutant can, therefore, be quantified by coupling a preconcentration system to a sensitive, selective detection/estimation technique³. In this regard the most widely used techniques includes solvent extraction⁴, coprecipitation^{5,6}, ion chromatography⁷, adsorption^{8,9}, cloud point extraction¹⁰, electrochemical deposition¹¹ and solid phase

extraction (SPE)^{12–14}. But, except SPE all other techniques may be ineffective or extremely expensive, when the metals are in large volumes of relatively low concentrations¹⁵. SPE^{16–18} is now one of the most interesting areas in analytical chemistry for the trace level separation and preconcentration of heavy metals, because it is eco-friendly, simple, selective, rapid and cost effective. SPE is based on the utilization of a major constituent as the supporting phase with different coating materials^{16–18} such as polyelectrolyte, high molecular mass carboxylic acid (HMMCA), chelating agent, surfactant, quaternary ammonium salt etc. The essential requirements of sorbents in SPE are (a) the possibility to extract selectively a large number of analytes over a wide pH range, (b) the quantitative sorption and elution ability, (c) the kinetically faster sorption and desorption mechanism, (d) the high retention capacity, (e) the regenerability, (f) the accessibility and (g) the mechanical and chemical stability¹⁹. Having these, quite a good deal of literature appears to deal with HMMCA on hydrophobic silica support for selective separation of metal ions^{17,20–23}. Silica gel is

found to act as a successful support since it does not swell or strain, has good mechanical strength and can undergo heat treatment²⁴. Versatic 9 is a mixture of highly branched saturated monocarboxylic acid²⁵ and it is soluble in several solvents like benzene, toluene, *n*-hexane, xylene, butanol, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, nitrobenzene and diisopropyl ether^{26,27}. It has a good thermal and chemical stability²⁵ and efficiently extracted metal ions from aqueous solution over a wide range of pH²⁶⁻²⁹. Solvent extraction behavior of Cu^{II} have been made with Versatic 9²⁶. But, solid phase extraction, preconcentration, separation and removal of Cu^{II} with this exchanger has yet not been reported. The present work reports a rapid method for the extraction, preconcentration and separation of microgram level Cu^{II} from wide variety of multi-component mixtures containing large number of heavy, toxic and congener cations with HMMCA, Versatic 9 on hydrophobic silica support.

Results and discussion

Effect of volume and flow-rate of the influent and common anions on extraction :

The volume of Cu^{II} solution up to 0.9 dm³ does not influence the percentage of retention. The complete retention of Cu^{II} at the column was found even at a flow rate of 3.5 cm³ min⁻¹. Common anions like Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻ up to 300 µg cm⁻³ and CH₃COO⁻ up to 350 µg cm⁻³ (Table 1) did not interfere in the extraction. The tolerance limit of the cations like Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Zn²⁺ are ~25 fold for the quantitative extraction (>92%) of Cu^{II}.

The systematic extraction chromatographic studies on

Table 1. Effect of interfering anions on extraction of Cu^{II}

Column = 0.8 × 8 cm, flow-rate = 1.0 mL min⁻¹, Cu^{II} taken = 10.6 µg, pH = 5.0

Interfering ion	Interfering ion concn. (µg mL ⁻¹)/Retention (%)					
	100	150	200	250	300	350
Cl ⁻	98.2	97.8	96.7	96.1	93.6	90.2
SO ₄ ²⁻	98.5	97.2	96.1	94.9	92.1	87.6
ClO ₄ ⁻	99.1	98.7	97.3	97.1	96.2	89.5
NO ₃ ⁻	99.4	99.1	98.5	98.4	97.6	91.4
CH ₃ COO ⁻	99.7	99.6	99.2	98.5	98.0	97.4
Co ²⁺	98.2	95.4	93.7	92.4	91.1	90.2
Cd ²⁺	97.8	95.6	94.2	92.1	90.7	78.4
Zn ²⁺	98.5	97.2	95.5	93.7	92.0	87.9
Ni ²⁺	99.2	97.6	95.7	93.2	90.5	88.2

Cu^{II} (10.6 µg) with Versatic 9 at the pH range 3.0-7.5 ensured its quantitative extraction at the optimum pH range 4.0-5.5. FTIR spectra of the exchanger containing -COOH group³⁰ shows a strong absorption at 1701 cm⁻¹. However, the position of this peak is shifted to lower range (1698-1627 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of Cu^{II} loaded exchanger. This decreasing of stretching frequency indicates the conversion of -COOH group to -COO⁻ ion³⁰ and suggesting the participation of this functional group in the adsorption of Cu^{II} by the exchanger. Both the neutral, [Cu(CH₃COO)₂] and cationic species, [Cu(CH₃COO)]⁺ are present³¹ at pH 4.0-5.5. At pH 4.5, plot of log K_d against log C_[CH₃COO⁻] gives a linear relationship (y = 1.012x + 1.605; R² = 0.9678) with slope of 1.012 at fixed concentration of extractant and fixed concentration of Cu^{II}. A linear relationship (y = 0.9833x + 1.5616; R² = 0.9812) with slope = 0.9833 between log K_d and log C_[Versatic 9] is also obtained at pH 4.5, at a fixed concentration of acetate and fixed concentration of Cu^{II}. At pH 4.0-6.5, Versatic 911 exists as a dimer³² in organic solvent. So the probable composition of the extracted species is 1 : 2 : 1 (metal : extractant : acetate). Bearing this in mind it has been suggested that Cu^{II} first produce the monomer, [Cu(CH₃COO)]⁺ with acetate ion at pH 4.0-5.5 and having suitable size and charge, this cationic monomer goes to the exchange site according to the following proposed path :

At pH higher than 5.5, Cu^{II} undergoes hydrolysis and does not participate in exchange process.

Effect of pH on distribution coefficient (K_d) : The distribution coefficient (K_d) at different pH have been computed using the following equation (eq. (3))³³ and the effect of pH on log K_d of Cu^{II} between the adsorbent and solution is shown in Fig. 1.

$$K_d (mL g^{-1}) = C_s (\mu g g^{-1})/C_{Sol} (\mu g mL^{-1}) \quad (3)$$

Here, C_s and C_{Sol} are concentration of Cu^{II} in the solid phase and in solution phase respectively.

At low pH values (<4.5), the lower values of log K_d were attributed to the difficult deprotonation of the carboxylic acid moiety of the exchanger which eliminates the ability of acetate ion to chelate with Cu^{II}. The low pH values also increase the solubility of Cu^{II} in aqueous so-

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_d$ vs pH at fixed concentration of Cu^{II} and extractant.

lution and agreed the suggested mechanistic path (eq. (2)). It is observed that $\log K_d$ for Cu^{II} (3.59) at pH 5.0 of the modified silica gel with Versatic 9 is much higher than the corresponding value 1.06 for active silica gel only.

Adsorption isotherm : Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models were fitted to the experimental data to investigate sorption capacity of the modified exchanger. Applicability of the isotherm equations were compared by using the correlation coefficients, R^2 . An experimental linear plot ($y = 0.0297x + 0.0998$; $R^2 = 0.9987$) of C_e/q_e versus C_e for the adsorbent suggest the applicability of the Langmuir adsorption (chemisorption) isotherm (eq. (4)) and indicates the formation of monolayer coverage of the sorbate at the outer surface of the sorbent with the value 33.67 (mg g⁻¹) and 0.297 (dm³ mg⁻¹) for the Langmuir constant Q_0 and b respectively.

$$C_e/q_e = 1/Q_0b + C_e/Q_0 \quad (4)$$

where, C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg dm⁻³) of Cu^{II} and q_e is the amount of Cu^{II} adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent (mg g⁻¹). Q_0 and b are the Langmuir constants describing the maximum adsorption (mg g⁻¹) and energy parameter of adsorption (dm³ mg⁻¹) respectively. However, the experimental plot (Fig. 2) of $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ gives no linear relation and denies the follow-

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log q_e$ vs $\log C_e$ [average curve].

ing Freundlich isotherm models (eq. (5)). Moreover the value of $1/n$ for the average curve is appreciably lower than unity (0.04). The correlation coefficient for Langmuir (0.9977) is very much higher than that of Freundlich value (0.7306). So, it becomes more and more difficult to adsorb additional adsorbates.

$$\log q_e = \log k_F + (1/n) \log C_e \quad (5)$$

Here, k_F and $1/n$ are the adsorption constants, indicators of adsorption capacity and adsorption intensity.

Effect of temperature on extraction : The extraction equilibrium constant (K_{ex}) has been computed at different temperatures using the following equation (eq. (4))³⁴ and plot of $\log K_{ex}$ vs $1000/T$ gives a linear relationship ($y = -2.823x + 14.25$; $R^2 = 0.960$).

$$K_{ex} = \frac{E_R}{[(RCOO)_2(H^+)_2]} [H^+] \quad (6)$$

where, $[(RCOO^-)_2(H^+)_2(S)]$, denotes the concentration of Versatic 9 in its dimeric form, participated in ion-exchange process, and E_R is the ratio of extracted metal ion to its un-extracted portion.

The effect of temperature on extraction of Cu^{II} has been made for the determination³⁴ of different thermodynamic parameters at pH 5.0 using the standard van't Hoff equation. The enthalpy change (ΔH) was evaluated from the plot of $\log K_{ex}$ vs $1000/T$.

The free energy change (ΔG) and entropy change (ΔS) at room temperature (298 K) were calculated. The positive ΔH (0.054 kJ mol⁻¹) and smaller ΔS (0.09 kJ mol⁻¹) rationalizes the endothermic nature of the extraction process¹⁵. During the adsorption of Cu^{II}, H⁺ is released in the solution phase and increases the number of neutral CH₃COOH. This effect correlates with positive value of ΔS . The higher negative value of ΔG (-26.87 kJ mol⁻¹) suggests the spontaneity and tendency of chemisorptions of the equilibrium³⁵, and is an agreement of Langmuir isotherm.

After extraction, to select the specific stripping agents, Cu^{II} was stripped with demineralized water and various acids of different concentrations. The systematic studies on stripping behavior gave the quantitative elution of Cu^{II} with HNO₃ and HCl of concentration ≥ 0.1 M and with CH₃COOH of concentration ≥ 0.5 M (Table 2). During experiment it was found that 0.1 M HNO₃ gave the best stripping (least required volume, 10 mL), hence it was used as stripping agent in the further steps of experi-

Table 2. Stripping behavior of Cu^{II} with respect to different eluents

Column = 0.8 × 8 cm, flow-rate = 1.0 mL min⁻¹, Cu^{II} taken = 10.6 µg, pH = 5.0

Eluents	Concn. (M)	V _{max} (mL)	V _t (mL)	Recovery ^a (%)
H ₂ O	-	-	-	-
HNO ₃	0.01	60	100	20.2
	0.02	50	80	48.1
	0.03	25	60	74.7
	0.05	15	35	82.6
	0.1	5	10	98.6
HCl	0.01	45	100	18.5
	0.02	45	90	64.5
	0.03	35	80	67.6
	0.05	30	60	76.7
	0.1	15	45	98.0
CH ₃ COOH	0.05	55	120	0.3
	0.1	40	90	4.8
	0.2	35	60	8.8
	0.3	25	50	38.6
	1.0	15	30	78.4
	1.5	12	25	88.6

^aAverage of five determinations.

The elution process (back extraction) follows the reverse reaction of extraction (eq. (2)) and Cu^{II} is eluted with H⁺. Acetic acid dissociates weakly in aqueous solution and that is why it requires relatively higher concentration compared to the strong inorganic acids like HCl or HNO₃ for the quantitative elution of Cu^{II}. Moreover, low level of the mineral acids elute Cu^{II} from the exchanger bed through the formation of nitro³¹, Cu(NO₃)⁺ and corresponding chloro cations.

The extraction of 0.02–0.04 mg mL⁻¹ of Cu^{II} on HMMCA, Versatic 9 in the pH range 4.5–5.5 (Table 3) showed that the preconcentration factor (PF), ratio of effluent concentration to sample concentration (C_f/C_s) increased with increase in volume of the sample. At a constant volume of sample, the PF was independent of pH and sample concentration. The recovery decreased with increase in sample volume. Up to a sample volume 1200 mL, the recovery of Cu^{II} was quantitative (>95%) with a PF of about 114. To reach the breakthrough values 30.6 mg (at pH 4.5), 36.9 mg (at pH 5.0) and 45.0 mg (at pH 5.5), respectively 1532 mL of 0.02 g L⁻¹, 1317 mL of 0.028 g L⁻¹ and 1250 mL of 0.036 g L⁻¹ of sample were passed, when the recoveries were found to be poor. Thus, PF did not attain its maximum possible

Table 3. Effect of volume, sample concentration and pH on preconcentration factor

pH	Sample concn. (C _s) (mg mL ⁻¹)	Sample volume (V _s) (mL)	Flow-rate = 1.0 mL min ⁻¹ , pH = 5.0, Cu ^{II} = 0.02–0.04 mg mL ⁻¹		Effluent concn. (C _f) (g L ⁻¹)	Recovery ^a (%)	PF (C _f /C _s)
			Amount of Cu ^{II} (mg)				
			Added	Recovered			
4.5	0.020	800	16.0	15.81	1.58	98.8	79.0
		900	18.0	17.68	1.77	98.2	88.5
		1000	20.0	19.40	1.94	97.6	97.0
		1100	22.0	21.29	2.13	96.8	106.5
		1200	24.0	22.94	2.29	95.6	114.5
		1300	26.0	22.75	2.27	87.5	113.5
		1400	28.0	21.73	2.17	77.6	108.5
		1532	30.6	21.51	2.15	70.3	107.5
5.0	0.025	800	20.0	19.84	1.98	99.2	79.2
		900	22.5	22.05	2.21	98.0	88.4
		1000	25.0	24.38	2.44	97.5	97.6
		1100	27.5	26.73	2.67	97.2	106.8
		1200	30.0	28.59	2.86	95.3	114.4
		1300	32.5	28.54	2.85	87.8	114.0
		1392	34.8	27.32	2.73	78.5	109.2
5.5	0.030	800	24.0	23.88	2.39	99.5	79.7
		900	27.0	26.51	2.65	98.2	88.3

1000	30.0	29.22	2.92	97.4	97.3
1100	33.0	32.01	3.20	97.0	106.7
1200	36.0	34.27	3.43	95.2	114.3
1290	38.7	34.21	3.42	88.4	114.0

^aAverage of five determinations; PF = ratio of effluent concn. to sample concn. (C_f/C_s).

Standard deviation < 0.07.

Table 4. R_f values of different metal ions on Whatman No. 1 impregnated with Versatic 911

Time = 2.5 h, pH = 5.0, developing solvent = acetate buffer : acetone (25 : 1 v/v)

Cations	R_f values	Affinity order (increasing) ↓	Cations	R_f values	Affinity order (increasing) ↓
Ca ^{II}	0.97	Sn ^{II}	Hg ^{II}	0.18	Cu ^{II}
Mg ^{II}	0.95	Ca ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	0.42	Al ^{III}
Co ^{II}	0.96	Co ^{II}	Al ^{III}	0.30	Ga ^{III}
Zn ^{II}	0.93	Mg ^{II}	Ga ^{III}	0.24	Hg ^{II}
Cd ^{II}	0.90	Ni ^{II}	Tl ^{III}	0.10	Bi ^{III}
Pb ^{II}	0.55	Zn ^{II}	Bi ^{III}	0.13	Tl ^{III}
Sn ^{II}	0.98	Cr ^{III}	Fe ^{IIIa}	0.51	Cu ^{IIa}
Cr ^{III}	0.91	Cd ^{II}	Cu ^{IIa}	0.95	Fe ^{IIIa}
Ni ^{II}	0.92	Pb ^{II}	Zr ^{IVa}	0.10	Zr ^{IVa}

^apH = 2.5.

values 153, 131.7 and 125 at pH 4.5, 5.0 and 5.5 respectively as the recoveries were less than 100%. However, PF has been optimized at about 114.

Ion-exchange paper chromatography : At pH 5.0, the R_f values of metal ions were determined in acetate buffer-acetone mixture (15 : 2 v/v) on chromatogram (Table 4). Result shows that under this recommended condition Sn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} are very weakly bound (R_f value ~ 0.9) and metal ions like Pb^{II}, Al^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ga^{III} are moderately bound (R_f value 0.3–0.6) while Hg^{II}, Bi^{III}, Tl^{III} are tightly bound (R_f value < 0.2) with the stationary phase. At pH 2.5 binding strength of Zr^{IV} is very much higher than Fe^{III} and under this condition³¹, [Cu(H₂O)₆]²⁺ is very weakly bound with the stationary phase. At pH ~ 5.0 Sn^{II} exist as an anionic complex³⁶, [Sn(CH₃COO)₃]⁻ and moves at the fastest rate with the mobile phase. Aqua Cr^{III} is quite acidic (pK = 4) and at pH ~ 5.0 the hydroxo monomer [Cr(OH)(H₂O)₅]²⁺ equilibrates with hydroxo dimer, [Cr₂(μ-OH)₂(H₂O)₈]⁴⁺³⁷. These different cationic species probably equilibrates with the exchange site and compared to Sn^{II} moves at slower rate. With acetate ion the complexity constant for Ca^{II} is much higher than that for Mg^{II}³⁷. So Ca^{II} moves at a faster rate than Mg^{II}. [M(H₂O)₆]³⁺ are acidic and the constants³⁹ K_A for Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} respectively, are 10⁻⁵, 10⁻³, 10⁻⁴ and 10⁻¹. The aqua ion, [M(H₂O)₆]³⁺

protonates quickly the acetate ion and the conjugate base [M(OH)(H₂O)₅]²⁺ is produced³⁷ with their formation order, [Tl(OH)(H₂O)₅]²⁺ >> [Ga(OH)(H₂O)₅]²⁺ > [Al(OH)(H₂O)₅]²⁺. These monomers quickly equilibrates with their corresponding dimmers³⁷, [M₂(H₂O)₈(μ-OH)₂]⁴⁺. It is suggested that these hydroxo species goes to the exchange site at the recommended pH. The most easily formed [Tl(OH)(H₂O)₅]²⁺ binds preferably with the exchange site and its movement in the mobile phase is slowest. While [Al(OH)(H₂O)₅]²⁺ with its lowest formation tendency moves at the fastest rate. Aqua ions of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} are quite acidic and the constants³⁷ K_A for Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} respectively, are 10⁻⁹, 10⁻¹⁰ and 10⁻⁴. The aqua ion, [M(H₂O)₆]²⁺ protonate quickly the acetate ion, and their corresponding hydroxo species, [M(OH)(H₂O)₅]⁺ are produced³⁷ and equilibrated during the development of chromatogram. The increasing affinity order is directly related to decreasing order of their hydrated radii (Kielland³⁸). At pH ~ 5.0, aqua Cu^{II} produced monomeric acetato complex³¹, [Cu(CH₃COO)]⁺ like lead(II)³⁹ and both were participated in the exchange process. However, the formation tendency of lead complex is much higher than the corresponding copper complex⁴⁰ and moves at a faster rate with the mobile phase. At pH 2.5, Cu^{II} is not present as [Cu(CH₃COO)]⁺³³ and

does not participate in the exchange process and moves at the fastest rate with the mobile phase. Under this recommended condition, aqua $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ gives μ -oxo dimer³⁷, $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{FeOFe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{4+}$, as the main species during its equilibration with stationary phase and moves moderately. While under this high acidic condition (low pH), zirconium(IV) exist as a tetramer⁴¹, $[\text{Zr}_4(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{16}]^{8+}$. Having high charge density and suitable size tetramer goes to exchange site quickly and moves at the slowest rate.

Separation of Cu^{II} from binary mixtures : Cu^{II} was separated from several metal ions in binary mixtures. The separations were achieved either by exploiting the difference in pH for extraction or by using suitable stripping agent utilizing the R_f values. When, Cu^{II} - Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} - Zr^{IV} binary mixtures were passed through the column at pH 2.5, only Cu^{II} ($R_f > 0.95$) from the said mixtures was percolated through the column with the mobile phase. The quantitatively extracted Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} were eluted with 0.5 M H_2SO_4 and 6 M HNO_3 respectively as $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ and ZrO^{2+} ion⁴¹ and follows their affinity order (Table 4). Binary mixtures containing Cu^{II} with Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} when equilibrated with the exchanger at pH 5.0, the diverse ions ($R_f > 0.92$) passed through the column with the mobile phase. However, at pH 5.0 from the binary mixtures the diverse ions like Pb^{II} , Bi^{III} , Al^{III} , Ga^{III} , In^{III} , Tl^{III} , Hg^{II} , Ce^{IV} and Th^{IV} were extracted along with Cu^{II} (R_f values < 0.6). From these respective mixtures, Cu^{II} was separated by using different selective eluents. From Cu^{II} - Bi^{III} , Cu^{II} - Al^{III} , Cu^{II} - Tl^{III} , Cu^{II} - Hg^{II} , Cu^{II} - Ce^{IV} and Cu^{II} - Th^{IV} binary mixtures Cu^{II} was eluted first with 0.1 M HNO_3 and subsequently Bi^{III} , Al^{III} , Tl^{III} , Hg^{II} , Ce^{IV} and Th^{IV} were eluted with 1 M HCl , 1 M CH_3COOH , 0.5 M HCl , 1 M H_2SO_4 , 0.4 M H_2SO_4 and 2 M HNO_3 respectively. However, Cu^{II} was eluted first with 1.2 M CH_3COOH from the respective mixtures of Cu^{II} - Ga^{III} and Cu^{II} - In^{III} . Then Ga^{III} and In^{III} were eluted with 0.5 M HNO_3 and 2.5 M CH_3COOH respectively. In the case of Cu^{II} - Pb^{II} binary mixture, sequentially Pb^{II} and Cu^{II} were eluted 0.01 M CH_3COOH and 0.1 M HNO_3 .

Separation of Cu^{II} from multi-component mixtures : In order to assess the possible analytical applications, the proposed method was applied to separate Cu^{II} from multi-component synthetic mixtures containing Cu^{II} with different metal ions commonly associated with it in same analytical group, ores and alloy samples. Separation of

Cu^{II} from diverse metal ions in binary and multi-component synthetic mixtures follows the R_f values and Kielland principle⁴⁰, 'affinity order of the cations for cation-exchange resin is approximately the order of their hydrated ionic radii' and also the Ketell principle⁴²; 'decrease of distribution coefficient (K_d) occurs with the complexation tendency of anion in mobile phase'.

Sequential separation of Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Sn^{II} , Bi^{III} and Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} : Prior to column experiment, paper chromatography was done and best resolution of ions was found with respect to R_f values at pH ~ 5.0 in acetate buffer (Table 5) in the chromatogram. At pH 5.0 when the synthetic mixture containing Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Sn^{II} and Bi^{III} passed through the column, only Sn^{II} passed through the column as carboxylate anion complex³⁶, $[\text{Sn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3]^-$.

Table 5. Ratio of R_f values of Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Hg^{II} , Sn^{II} and Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Bi^{III} , Cd^{II} in acetate buffer at different pHs

Time = 2.5 h, Temp. = 25 °C			
Metal ions	pH	R_f values	Ratio of R_f
Sn^{II}	4.5	0.89; 0.63; 0.47; 0.14	6.35; 4.50; 3.36; 1
Pb^{II}	5.0	0.97; 0.55; 0.42; 0.11	8.82; 5.00; 3.82; 1
Bi^{III}	5.5	0.94; 0.49; 0.39; 0.13	7.23; 3.77; 3.00; 1
Cd^{II}	4.5	0.90; 0.63; 0.47; 0.23	3.91; 2.74; 2.04; 1
Pb^{II}	5.0	0.91; 0.55; 0.42; 0.18	5.06; 3.05; 2.33; 1
Hg^{II}	5.5	0.87; 0.49; 0.39; 0.21	4.14; 2.33; 1.85; 1

Sequential elution of Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} have been made with 0.01 M CH_3COOH , 0.1 M HNO_3 and 1 M HCl respectively. Synthetic mixture containing Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} when equilibrated with the exchanger at pH 5.0, except Cd^{II} all the metal ions along with Cu^{II} were quantitatively extracted at the column. The higher sized mercuric cation (lower hydrated radii) present as hydroxo cation³⁷, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ and goes to the exchanger site with higher affinity³⁸. Sequential elution of Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} has been made with 0.01 M CH_3COOH , 0.1 M HNO_3 and 1 M H_2SO_4 respectively. For all other quaternary synthetic mixtures, metal ions are separated by a two steps extraction process. At pH 2.5 from the solution only Fe^{III} was extracted while other three ions percolate through the column. The effluent containing the three unextracted ions was again equilibrated with the exchanger at pH 5.0 and separated each other with selective eluents (Table 6, Fig. 3).

Table 6. Separation of Cu^{II} from multi-component synthetic mixturesColumn = 0.8 × 8 cm, flow-rate = 1.0 mL min⁻¹, Cu^{II} taken = 10.6 µg, pH = 5.0

Metal ions	Weight of the metal ions (µg)		Recovery (%)	Relative error (%)	Eluent used	Eluent volume (mL)
	Added	Recovered ^a				
Zr ^{IVb}	3574	3608	100.95	0.95	6 M HNO ₃	15
Co ^{II}	3266	3233	98.99	-1.01	Mobile phase	30
Cu ^{II}	10.60	10.78	101.7	1.69	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Bi ^{III}	3224	3269	101.4	1.39	1 M HCl	20
Zr ^{IVb}	3574	3624	101.4	1.39	6 M HNO ₃	15
Ni ^{II}	4280	4206	98.27	-1.73	Mobile phase	30
Cu ^{II}	10.60	10.76	101.5	1.51	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Bi ^{III}	3804	3769	99.08	-0.92	1 M HCl	20
Zr ^{IVb}	3574	3616	101.1	1.08	6 M HNO ₃	15
Cd ^{II}	3740	3682	98.75	-1.27	Mobile phase	50
Cu ^{II}	10.60	10.72	101.1	1.13	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Tl ^{III}	3804	3748	98.73	-1.28	0.5 M HCl	20
Zr ^{IVb}	3574	3626	101.45	1.45	6 M HNO ₃	15
Zn ^{II}	3160	3118	98.67	-1.33	Mobile phase	30
Cu ^{II}	10.60	10.44	98.49	-1.51	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Hg ^{II}	3744	3696	98.72	-1.28	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	20
Fe ^{IIIb}	3574	3618	101.23	1.23	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	50
Cd ^{II}	3350	3398	98.95	-1.06	Mobile phase	50
Cu ^{II}	10.60	10.78	101.7	1.69	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Th ^{IV}	2788	2758	98.92	-1.08	2 M HNO ₃	30
Fe ^{IIIb}	3574	3628	101.51	1.51	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	50
Cr ^{III}	3840	3886	101.19	1.19	Mobile phase	30
Cu ^{II}	10.60	10.52	99.24	-0.75	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Hg ^{II}	3826	3778	98.75	-1.25	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	20
Cd ^{II}	3834	3898	101.67	1.67	Mobile phase	50
Pb ^{II}	4764	4832	101.4	-1.43	0.01 M CH ₃ COOH	12
Cu ^{II}	10.6	10.79	101.7	1.79	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Hg ^{II}	3000	2956	98.53	-1.47	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	20
Sn ^{II}	3860	3908	101.24	1.24	Mobile phase	50
Pb ^{II}	2844	2894	101.7	1.44	0.01 M CH ₃ COOH	12
Cu ^{II}	10.6	10.42	98.30	-1.69	0.1 M HNO ₃	10
Bi ^{III}	3006	2978	99.07	-0.93	1 M HCl	20

^aAverage of five determinations; standard deviation < 0.05; ^bpH = 2.5.

The effectiveness of the proposed method was judged by separating Cu^{II} from some standard alloy samples. The feasibility of the process was tested with the effluent obtained from a typical electroplating industry. High degree of preconcentration (800 mL to 10 ml) (>70 fold) with subsequent removal, or recovery (>91%) of Cu^{II} and the associated metals with low standard deviation

(<0.4) for industrial and standard alloy samples were obtained (Table 7). Separation of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} in water (waste, thermal and tap water) samples was performed by applying the proposed method (Table 8). After removal, recovery from effluent and alloy samples, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} were determined by ion selective electrode, while Sn^{II} was determined spectrophotometrically.

Fig. 3. (a-f) Chromatograms of some important multi-component mixtures.

Table 7. Preconcentration, removal, recovery of Pb^{II} and Cu^{II}/Sn^{II} from industrial and alloy samples

pH = 5.0, flow-rate = 1.0 mL min⁻¹, column = 0.8 × 8 cm, sample volume = 800 mL, elution volume = 10 mL

Samples/ composition	Separation of Pb ^{II}		Separation of Sn ^{IIa} /Cu ^{IIb} /Zn ^{IIc}	
	Found (%)	Recovery (%) [#]	Found (%)	Recovery (%) [#]
Leaded gunmetal/ Pb ^{II} = 3.3 Sn ^{II} = 5.06 Cu ^{II} = 85.2 (in %)	2.99	90.60	4.74 ^a	93.7 ^a
		(sd = 0.37)		(sd = 0.40)
		(PF = 60.4)	82.3 ^b	96.6 ^b
				(PF = 77.3 ^b)
Lead concentrates (42dG)/ Pb ^{II} = 59.5 Cu ^{II} = 0.36	57.12	96.0	15.82 ^c	92.5 ^c
		(sd = 0.38)		(sd = 45)
		(PF = 64.0)	0.33 ^b	91.7 ^b
				(PF = 73.4 ^b ; sd = 0.41 ^b)

Zn ^{II} = 17.1 (in %)				
Brass 5 g/ Pb ^{II} = 2.23 Cu ^{II} = 67.4 (in %)	2.09 (sd = 0.36) (PF = 62.5)	93.72	63.9 ^b (sd = 0.32) (PF = 75.8)	94.8 ^b
Electroplating waste/ Pb ^{II} = 11.2 Cu ^{II} = 10.0 (in mg dm ⁻³)	10.2 (sd = 0.51) (PF = 60.7)	91.07	9.26 ^b (sd = 0.31) (PF = 74.1)	92.6 ^b

[#]Average of five determinations.

Table 8. Removal of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} in water samples
Sample volume = 300 cm³, elution volume = 10 mL

Sample	Water			Relative error (%)
	Metal ion	Added (µg)	Found ^a (µg)	
Waste water	Cu ^{II}	-	0.9	-
		20.5	19.6	8.41
Thermal water	Cd ^{II}	-	ND	-
		50.2	48.2	3.98
	Cu ^{II}	-	1.21	-
Well water		20.5	19.4	1.06
	Cd ^{II}	-	ND	-
		50.2	47.8	4.78
Well water	Cu ^{II}	-	1.43	-
		20.5	20.6	6.06
	Cd ^{II}	-	ND	-
	50.2	48.7	2.99	

^aAverage of five determinations.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Digital Elico LI-120 pH meter combined with glass electrode, 7D-1F thermostat, spectrophotometer (Beckman DU-6 ECIL GS 5700A), Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer (Model FTIR-8400S), Thermo Scientific (Orion 5 Star Benchtop Multi W/ISE mtr, Singapore), Perkin-Elmer atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Model Analyst 400) and chromatographic glass column (0.8 × 8 cm) with glass-wool plug at the bottom were used in the present study.

Unless otherwise stated, all chemicals and solvents used in this work were of analytical grade (BDH/E.

Merck). A liquid cation exchanger, Versatic 9 (Shell Chemical, London, England), a mixture of highly branched aliphatic C₉ was used without any further purification. Dimethyldichlorosilane (BDH, Bombay, India) was used to make the silica gel (BDH, Bombay, India) (120 mesh) hydrophobic. A standard stock solution of Cu^{II} (1.06 mg cm⁻³) was prepared by dissolving Cu(NO₃)₂ (E. Merck, Bombay, India) in water and estimated complexometrically⁴³ with EDTA (E. Merck, Bombay, India) using xylenol orange (BDH, Bombay, India) as indicator. The solution containing 10.6 µg cm⁻³ of Cu^{II} was prepared through appropriate dilution. This concentration (10.6 µg cm⁻³) of Cu^{II} has been selected randomly for our present work. Buffer solutions of different pHs were prepared from acetic acid (BDH, Bombay, India) (0.1 M) and ammonium acetate (BDH, Bombay, India) (0.1 M) in proper ratio. Lower pH values were adjusted with the help of 0.2 M chloroacetic acid.

Preparation of ion exchange material : Silica gel (120 mesh) was made hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapor of dimethyldichlorosilane (DMDCS) in N₂ atmosphere. The DMDCS treated (silanised) silica gel was then washed with anhydrous methanol and dried at 70–80 °C. The silanised silica gel was impregnated with Versatic 9, diluted in diisopropyl ether and was dried in a rotary vacuum evaporator to achieve uniform coating⁴⁴. Each column could be used for at least 30–40 cycles without any loss of its exchange capacity. For ion-exchange paper chromatography, 0.2 mL Versatic 9 was taken in 20 mL diisopropyl ether and paper strips (Whatman No. 1) were immersed in it to achieve uniform coating and then dried in air. Cu^{II} solution (in µg) was taken on the paper strip

containing exchanger and developed with acetate buffer (pH ~ 5.0) : acetone (15 : 2 v/v) as the developing solvent.

The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was determined²² at different temperatures by measuring the milliequivalent (meq) of sodium ions absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in H⁺ form. It was found to be 2.44 meq of H⁺ g⁻¹ of dry exchanger at the temperature range 27–40 °C.

Break through capacity and preconcentration factor :

The pHs of the exchanger bed and Cu^{II} solution (1.06 mg cm⁻³) was adjusted to the desired value with 0.1 M acetate buffer and then Cu^{II} solution in buffer was passed through the column containing 1 g of dry exchanger at a flow-rate of ~1.0 cm⁻³ min⁻¹ (20–25 drops min⁻¹). It was found that the leakage of Cu^{II} started at pHs 4.5, 5.0 and 5.5 after passing 28.9 cm⁻³ (30.6 mg), 32.8 cm⁻³ (34.8 mg) and 33.5 cm⁻³ (38.7 mg) of metal ion solution respectively. So the uptake of Cu^{II} in the column increases with the increase in pH. After saturation through extraction, Cu^{II} was eluted from column with 10 cm⁻³ 0.1 M HNO₃. During this continuous extraction, Cu^{II} has been accumulated gradually on the column from its influent of lower concentration (1.06 mg cm⁻³) and after elution the effluent (10 cm³) were found to be rich with Cu^{II} with higher concentrations (3.06 mg cm⁻³, 3.48 mg cm⁻³, 3.87 mg cm⁻³). So the method preconcentrates Cu^{II} in the effluent with a factor of ~2.9, 3.3 and 3.7 on milligram levels.

General extraction procedure : An aliquot of Cu^{II} solution (10.6 µg mL⁻¹) in acetate buffer of pH 5.0 was passed through the column (pre-adjusted pH 5.0) containing ion exchanger (1 g); at a flow rate of 1.0 cm³ min⁻¹. After extraction Cu^{II} was stripped with 0.1 M HNO₃ and the amount of Cu^{II} was determined by ion selective electrode.

Batch procedure :

Distribution coefficient (K_d) : A total 100 mg of the dry exchanger was suspended with constant stirring in 400 cm³ Cu^{II} solution (10.6 µg cm⁻³) for 30 min at the desired pH value in the range 2.5–7.5. The same experiment has also been made in presence of acetate ion in the range 50–300 ppm at pH 5.0. The supernatant was fil-

tered through a dry filter paper immediately. The amount of Cu^{II} in the filtrate was determined by ion selective electrode.

Adsorption isotherm : A total 100 mg of the dry exchanger was suspended with constant stirring for 30 min in 400 cm³ of Cu^{II} solution with different initial concentrations (10–80 µg cm⁻³) at pH 5.0. The amount of Cu^{II} adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent (q_e in mg g⁻¹) was computed using the following equation :

$$q_e = (C_1 - C_e)V/m \quad (1)$$

Here, C₁ and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentrations (mg dm⁻³), m is the mass (g) of the adsorbent and V (dm³) is the volume of the solution.

Conclusions :

The proposed method is eco-friendly, simple, cost effective, rapid and selective and needs only 2.5 h for complete work involving separation and estimation of Cu^{II}. Clean separation (Fig. 3a-f) of Cu^{II} has been achieved from several toxic and heavy metal ions like Pb^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Tl^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Ce^{IV} and Th^{IV}. The separation of Cu^{II} from these toxic, heavy and congener metals has great importance to the environmental and analytical chemists. The method was found selective at the optimized conditions for Cu^{II} and does not need separation of other constituents present in the matrix. Very minute amount (~0.2 mL) of liquid extractant in the developed exchanger can selectively separate Cu^{II} from these wide variety of multi-component mixtures containing large number of heavy, toxic and congener cations (Table 6). The developed exchanger is chemically stable (up to 6 M HNO₃, 4 M CH₃COOH, 4 M HCl and 2 M H₂SO₄) and effective over a wide range of pH. It can be used for more than 30–40 cycles without any loss its exchange capacity. These show its additional advantages over the other conventional exchangers^{12-18,46-51}. Recoveries of metal ions were quantitative (>99%), standard deviation was <0.07 and the relative error was within ±1.75%. However, the removal (%) and preconcentration factor of Cu^{II} for a typical electroplating waste were 92.6 and 74.1, respectively with a standard deviation of 0.31; and the corresponding values for Pb^{II} were 91.07, 60.7 and 0.51 respectively. A comparison of this exchanger with other matrices is given in Table 9.

Table 9. Comparison with the other preconcentration procedures of Pb^{II} and Cu^{II}

Support-immobilized ligand	Preconcentration factor		Ref.
	Pb ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	
Versatic 911-silanised silica gel	74.3–76.4 ^a	72.1–75.5 ^a , 114 ^b	This work
Poly(HEMA)-cibacron blue F3-GA	42	63	14
Versatic 10	46	42	20
XAD-1180-SA	100	150	45
XAD-2-quinalizarin	50	100	46
XAD-2- <i>o</i> -aminophenol	40	50	47
XAD-2-Triton	25	200	48
Silica gel- <i>N</i> -(3-propyl)- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine	100	100	49
Merrifield resin-calix[4]arene- <i>o</i> -vanillinthiosemicarbazone	111	100	50
Silica gel 60- <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	—	50	51

^aReal samples; ^bsynthetic samples.

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